

Life Cycle Assessment of Composites Additive Manufacturing using Recycled Materials

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Additive Manufacturing (AM): Environmental Perspective

Less input material
required; less waste
material generated

Interesting applications for aircraft, naval and automotive components

This presentation: AM of carbon fiber-reinforced thermoplastic composites

Technology: fused filament fabrication (FFF) 3D printing

Source of carbon fibers: virgin and recycled

Objective: analyze the environmental impacts of composites, using different composition scenarios, and different product functionality scenarios

Life Cycle Analysis (LCA)

During LCA:
Define value chain & system boundaries

ISO standardized methodology to estimate potential environmental impacts of processes or products, from a full life-cycle perspective

Life Cycle Analysis (LCA)

- During LCA:
- Define value chain & system boundaries
 - Define foreground and background data
 - Define functional unit as basis for comparison
 - Collect Data (Life Cycle Inventory)
 - Translate Data to Environmental Impacts
 - Quantify Environmental Impacts per category
 - Interpret & report findings

Case Study & Methodology

- Wider context: EuReComp (GA 101058089)
R6 strategy (Reuse, Repair, Refurbish, Remanufacture, Repurpose and Recycle)
Various sources of composites (aerospace, aeronautics, automotive, wind energy)
Interdisciplinary approach (market, logistics, technology, advanced modelling, sustainability, cost, risk)
Multiple scales (lab, pilot, demonstrator)
Open and Closed-Loop Recycling
- Today's presentation: Closed-loop recycling of chopped carbon fibers via solvolysis, compare virgin and recycled fibers for AM with 15% wt. carbon fiber content, not considering polymer re-use or dismantling process
- Composition of products: 3 scenarios
100% virgin fibers; 50% virgin fibers; 25% virgin fibers
- Product functionality/durability: 3 scenarios
same performance virgin and recycled fibers; 25% loss of functionality after recycling;
50% loss of functionality after recycling

System Boundaries

Repeat process multiple times to simulate durability scenarios

Supercritical Water Solvolysis

Plasma-enhanced Solvolysis

Preliminary data:

>97% fiber recovery
→ we assume 90%

<10% loss in fiber mechanical properties
→ we model 3 scenarios

Results: Solvolysis Vs. Landfilling

■ Landfill
■ Supercritical

Negative environmental impact (positive environmental performance) from avoided production of virgin fibers

Results: Solvolysis Vs. Landfilling

Results: Solvolysis Vs. Fiber Production

Both solvolysis processes have lower impact than virgin fiber manufacture and landfilling

Results: Performance over Life Cycle

Results: Performance over Life Cycle

Lower impact than conventional product, even after functionality loss for fibers

Results: Optimizing equipment use in FFF

High improvement potential

Opportunities to further improve environmental performance

Conclusion

- ❑ Solvolysis is a promising recycling method for composite materials
- ❑ Up to 48% decrease in global warming potential over entire lifecycle
- ❑ Electricity consumption main contributor to environmental impacts
- ❑ Opportunities to further improve performance by optimizing the use of equipment

Thank you

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